

An efficient pyrimidine-based colorimetric chemosensor for naked-eye recognition of copper in aqueous medium

Anamika Dhara^a, Nikhil Guchhait^{*b} and Subash Chandra Bhattacharya^{*a}

^aDepartment of Chemistry, Jadavpur University, Kolkata-700 032, India

^bDepartment of Chemistry, University of Calcutta, 92, Acharya Prafulla Chandra Road, Kolkata-700 009, India

E-mail : nguchhait@yahoo.com

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Abstract : A pyrimidine-based receptor 1-(9*H*-fluoren-9-ylidene)-2-(4,6-dimethylpyrimidin-2-yl)hydrazine (HPF) was designed for naked-eye detection of Cu²⁺ with high selectivity in the presence of other competitive metal ions. In aqueous solution, upon addition of Cu²⁺ to HPF a color change from yellow to wine-red due to complex formation. The detection limit (5.03×10^{-8} M) of HPF for Cu²⁺ ions is much lower than that recommended by WHO in drinking water (31.5 μM). The sensor shows consistent performance in a pH value range of 4 to 11. Moreover, test strips based on receptor HPF were fabricated, which could act as a handy and efficient Cu²⁺ test for “in-the-field” measurement of Cu²⁺.

Keywords : Colorimetric chemosensor, hydrazino pyrimidine, Cu²⁺ recognition, DFT study, test kits.

1. Introduction

The metal copper plays a significant role in the areas of biological, environmental, and chemical systems¹. It is the third most abundant metal after iron and zinc in the human body and it plays an important role in a number of biological processes, including iron absorption, haemopoiesis, various enzyme-catalyzed and redox reactions²⁻⁵. Thus, daily ingestion of copper is indispensable for our good health⁶. However, copper is extremely toxic to some organisms such as many bacteria and viruses. Owing to its toxicity to bacteria, elevated concentrations of copper impeded self-purification capability of the sea or rivers and destroy the biological reprocessing systems in water. On the other hand, unregulated overloading of copper can induce severe neurological diseases, including Alzheimer's, Parkinson's, Menkes', and Wilson's diseases⁷. The World Health Organization (WHO) has set the safe limit of copper in drinking water at 2 ppm (31.5 μM)⁸. Accordingly, facile tech-

niques, enabling professionals to monitor the concentration of copper ions in environmental water samples and visualize its subcellular distribution in physiological processes, are of considerable significance for environment protection and human health.

For effortlessness, convenience and low cost, the fabrication of small molecular chemosensors into colorimetric test kits is highly challenging⁹. Even though some colorimetric/fluorescent chemosensors have been developed for the detection of Cu²⁺ so far, the sensing methods for fast detection of Cu²⁺ in aqueous solution, especially using colorimetric sensors without resorting to instruments, are relatively rare. Current approaches for environmental and clinical samples rely on costly, time-consuming methods like atomic absorption/emission spectroscopy¹⁰ or inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry¹¹ which are not very convenient and handy for “in-field” detection. Moreover, in most cases the sensing experiments are carried out using metal solutions in water and organic solvent

mixture¹² and hence are of greater academic interest than practical. Therefore, to develop simple-to-use and naked-eye diagnostic tool for selective detection of copper in aqueous medium is a demanding and attractive topic. Keeping in mind, we have chosen to design a fluorenone-appended pyrimidine based scaffold **HPF** as a receptor. Because of chemosensors based on pyrimidine are being widely studied in recent years owing to their great variety of biological activity ranging from antimalarial, antibacterial, antitumoral, antiviral activities, etc.^{13,14} which have often been associated to their chelating capability with trace metal ions. The higher (π) acidity of pyrimidine and presence of more than one hetero atom in the same ring take part in an important role in its coordination chemistry^{15–17}. On the other hand, fluorenone family compounds are base materials for the production of dyes and optical brightening agents. Fluorenones have been used extensively as catalyst precursors for electro-catalytic oxidation¹⁸, inhibition of DNA tumor viruses¹⁹, light-emitting materials²⁰, etc., but have rarely been used as chemical sensors. Fluorenone has been investigated as an attractive element in organic solar cells and display devices. This has led us to design and synthesize a colorimetric sensor containing a fluorenone framework that is particularly suitable for environmental and biological applications.

In the current paper, we report the synthesis, characterization, and sensing properties of **HPF** as a selective colorimetric receptor for detection of Cu^{2+} . The receptor **HPF** displayed a highly selective and sensitive (detection limit 5.03×10^{-8} M) colorimetric recognition toward Cu^{2+} by a change in the color from yellow to wine red in an aqueous solution with the formation ligand metal complex. Moreover, **HPF** can also be used as a practical, visible colorimetric detection kit for Cu^{2+} . So far our knowledge is concerned, this is one of the rare examples of the pyrimidine derivative employed for the detection of Cu^{2+} .

2. Experimental

2.1. Materials

9H-Fluorene-9-one was purchased from Aldrich. 2-Hydrazinyl-4,6-dimethyl pyrimidine was previously prepared in the laboratory²¹. Other commercially available chemicals and solvents were used and purified by standard procedure. Perchlorate salts of some cations such as Na^+ , K^+ , Mg^{2+} , Li^+ , Ag^+ , Al^{3+} , Pb^{2+} , Cr^{3+} , Mn^{2+} , Fe^{2+} , Fe^{3+} , Co^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Cu^{2+} , Zn^{2+} , Cd^{2+} and Hg^{2+} were purchased from Merck.

2.2. Apparatus

Elemental analyses (carbon, hydrogen and nitrogen) were performed with a Perkin-Elmer CHN analyzer 2400. Melting points were determined using a Buchi 530 melting apparatus. NMR spectra were recorded on a Bruker spectrometer at 500 (^1H NMR) MHz and 300 (^{13}C NMR) in $\text{DMSO}-d_6$. Chemical shifts (δ values) were reported in ppm down field from internal Me_4Si . The electronic spectra were recorded in MeOH-water solution on a Hitachi model U-3501 spectrophotometer. IR spectra (KBr pellet, 400–4000 cm^{-1}) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer model 883 infrared spectrophotometer.

2.3. Synthesis

2.3.1. Synthesis of reference compound REF

9H-Fluorene-9-one (200 mg, 1.109 mmol) was added to a methanol solution (5 mL) of 1-phenylhydrazine (0.109 mL, 1.109 mmol). The above mixture was refluxed at 80 °C for 2 h, then the resulting mixture was cooled to ambient temperature. Crude product was obtained and filtered off, then washed with methanol several times and dried under vacuum. The final compound **REF** was obtained as yellow crystalline solid (Scheme 1). Yield : 0.147 g, 48.5%; ^1H NMR (300 MHz, $\text{DMSO}-d_6$) : 10.77 (1H, s), 8.24 (1H, d, $J=7.65$ Hz), 7.94 (1H, d, $J=7.45$ Hz), 7.87 (1H, d, $J=7.40$ Hz), 7.81 (1H, d, $J=7.45$ Hz), 7.45 (1H, t, $J=0.75$ Hz, 6.8 Hz), 7.44–7.39 (2H, m), 7.37 (1H, d, $J=0.80$ Hz), 6.82 (1H, s), 2.40 (6H, s); ^{13}C NMR (300 MHz,

DMSO- d_6) δ (ppm) : 31.14, 114.58, 120.91, 121.58, 126.26, 128.47, 129.79, 138.23, 140.42, 145.75; Anal. Calcd. for $C_{19}H_{14}N_2$: C, 84.43; H, 5.23; N, 10.48%. Found : C, 84.42; H, 5.22; N, 10.36%.

2.3.2. Synthesis of receptor HPF

The compound **3** was synthesized following a literature method²¹. To a solution of 9H-fluoren-9-one (1 g, 5.55 mmol) in 10 mL of methanol, then previously prepared 1-(4,6-dimethylpyrimidin-2-yl)hydrazine (0.77 g, 5.55 mmol) was added to the mixture and cooled in ice water. Then glacial acetic acid (5 drops) was added to the mixture drop by drop with continuous stirring. Finally the total reaction mixture was refluxed at 90 °C for 12 h. The reaction mixture was cooled to room temperature. The yellow colored crystalline compound was separated out (Scheme 1). The solution was filtered and the compound was collected and dried in vacuum desiccators. Bright yellow solid of **HPF** was obtained. Yield : 0.72 g, 43.37%; ¹H NMR (500 MHz, DMSO- d_6) : 10.77 (1H, s), 8.24 (1H, d, $J=7.65$ Hz), 7.94 (1H, d, $J=7.45$ Hz), 7.87 (1H, d, $J=7.40$ Hz), 7.81 (1H, d, $J=7.45$ Hz), 7.45 (1H, t, $J=0.75$ Hz, 6.8 Hz), 7.44–7.39 (2H, m), 7.37 (1H, d, $J=0.80$ Hz), 6.82 (1H, s), 2.40 (6H, s); ¹³C

NMR (300 MHz, DMSO- d_6) δ (ppm) : 23.87, 31.06, 40.75, 113.75, 120.47, 120.84, 121.73, 127.17, 128.38, 129.62, 129.89, 130.69, 137.59, 139.09, 141.05, 146.03, 160.69, 168.10; IR (KBr) : 1527, 1437, 1336, 1183, 1122, 1085, 1029, 953 cm^{-1} . Anal. Calcd. for $C_{19}H_{16}N_4$: C, 76.10; H, 5.42; N, 18.66%. Found : C, 75.98; H, 5.37; N, 18.65%.

2.4. General procedure for UV-Vis titration

Stock solution of the receptor, **HPF** was prepared in 10 mM HEPES buffer-CH₃OH (99 : 1, v/v) at room temperature in the concentration range of 10^{-5} mol/L. 2 ml of the receptor (**HPF**) solution was taken in the cuvette. Stock solutions of guests in the concentration range of 10^{-5} M, were prepared in the same solvents and were individually added in different amounts to the receptor solution. The same stock solution of receptor and guests were used to perform the UV-Vis at 25 °C.

2.5. Job plot measurements

Copper perchlorate and **HPF** were dissolved in 10 mM HEPES buffer-CH₃OH (99 : 1, v/v) to make the concentrations 20 μ M. Volumes of 5.0, 4.5, 4.0, 3.5, 3.0, 2.5, 2.0, 1.5, 1.0, 0.5 and 0 mL of the solution

Scheme 1. Synthesis of receptor **HPF** and reference compound **REF**.

of **HPF** were taken and transferred to vials. Volumes of 0, 0.5, 1.0, 1.5, 2.0, 2.5, 3.0, 3.5, 4.0, 4.5 and 5.0 mL of the copper solutions were added to separate solutions of **HPF**. Each vial had a total volume of 5 mL. After shaking the vials for a few seconds, UV-Vis spectra were taken at room temperature.

2.6. Association/binding constant

The binding constant²² of the [Cu²⁺-**HPF**] complex was determined using the Benesi-Hildebrand (B-H) plot.

$$1/(A - A_0) = 1/\{K (A_{\max} - A_0) C\} + 1/(A_{\max} - A_0) \quad (1)$$

A_0 is the absorbance of **HPF** at absorbance maxima ($\lambda = 428$ nm), A is the observed absorbance at that particular wavelength in the presence of a certain concentration of the metal ion (C), A_{\max} is the maximum absorbance value that was obtained at $\lambda = 428$ nm during titration with varying $[C]$, K is the association constant (M^{-1}) and was determined from the slope of the linear plot, and $[C]$ is the concentration of the Cu²⁺ ion added during titration studies. The goodness of the linear fit of the B-H plot of $1/(A - A_0)$ vs $1/[Cu^{2+}]$ for 1 : 1 complex formation confirms the binding stoichiometry between **HPF** and Cu²⁺.

2.7. Detection limit

The detection limit²³ (DL) of **HPF** for Cu²⁺ was determined using the following equation :

$$DL = K^* Sb/S \quad (2)$$

where $K^* = 2$ or 3 (we take 3 in this case), Sb is the standard deviation of the blank solution and S is the slope of the calibration curve.

2.8. Crystallographic measurements

Measurements were done on a Bruker SMART APEX II CCD area detector equipped with graphite monochromated $M_o K_{\alpha}$ radiation ($k = 0.71073$ Å) source in ω scan mode at 296 K. The structure of the receptor **HPF** were solved using the SHELXS-97 pack-

age of programs and refined by the full-matrix least square technique based on F^2 in SHELXL-97²⁴. All non-hydrogen atoms were refined anisotropically. Positions of hydrogen atoms attached to carbon atoms were fixed at their ideal position.

3. Results and discussion

The compound **REF** (reference compound) was synthesized by refluxing 1-phenylhydrazine and 9H-fluoren-9-one in methanol and characterized by ¹H NMR, ¹³C NMR and CHN elemental analysis (Figs. S1-S2, in Supplementary material). The compound **3** was synthesized following a literature method and characterized by ¹H NMR spectra, Mass data, and FT-IR spectra²¹. We have synthesized pyrimidine-based receptor **HPF** (Scheme 1) by condensing hydrazino pyrimidine (**3**) and 9-fluorenone in methanol. The structure **HPF** was established by ¹H NMR, ¹³C NMR, FT-IR, CHN elemental analysis and Mass spectrometry techniques (Figs. S3-S6 in Supplementary material) and also X-ray crystal structure analysis (Fig. 1). We obtained single crystal for receptor **HPF** by slow evaporation of DMF/ether (1 : 1 v/v) over a period of one week and crystallized in a monoclinic $P2_1/c$ space group (Tables S1 and S2 in Supplementary material). The crystal structure of **HPF** (CCDC 1050465) is shown in Fig. 1. The C-N and N-N distances for **HPF** are in the range of 1.30–1.38 Å. Two adjacent **HPF** recep-

Fig. 1. Molecular structure of the receptor **HPF**.

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tors were connected via two types intermolecular hydrogen bonding interactions with N1-H---O1 and O1-H---O2 having distances of 2.991 Å and 2.839 Å, forming a 1D polymeric structure (Fig. 2a and 2b).

Fig. 2(a). H-bonding network within the dimeric unit of receptor **HPF**.

Fig. 2(b). 1D polymer through intermolecular H-bonding.

3.1. Visual sensing of Cu^{2+}

Visual color change of receptor **HPF** and reference compound **REF** (20 μM) were investigated in an aqueous medium [10 mM HEPES buffer- CH_3OH (99 : 1, v/v) at room temperature]. Upon addition of Cu^{2+} ion to **HPF**, a detectable naked-eye color change was observed from yellow to wine red (Fig. 3). Simultaneously, no naked-eye color change was observed upon addition of Cu^{2+} to the **REF** (inset of Fig. 7). Complexation does not occur between **REF** and Cu^{2+} due to the absence of pyrimidine 'N' in **REF**. Hence it can be said that pyrimidine 'N' is responsible for complexation. Other ions did not exhibit any detectable color change.

The sensing abilities of **HPF** (20 μM) toward various cations (Na^+ , K^+ , Li^+ , Mg^{2+} , Ag^+ , Al^{3+} , Pb^{2+} , Cr^{3+} , Mn^{2+} , Fe^{2+} , Fe^{3+} , Co^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Cu^{2+} , Zn^{2+} , Cd^{2+} and Hg^{2+}) were investigated by UV-Vis spectroscopy in an aqueous medium [10 mM HEPES buffer- CH_3OH (99 : 1, v/v) at room temperature]. Upon the addition of 1.2 equiv. of each cation, only Cu^{2+} induced distinct spectral change is observed, while the aforementioned other metal ions did not show colour change or slight change in the absorption spectra relative to the free receptor **HPF** (Fig. 4). For comparison, their optical densities at 428 nm upon addition of the above mentioned cations to **HPF** solution are charted in Fig. 5.

The absorption spectrum of receptor **HPF** (20 μM) exhibits strong absorption bands at 360 nm, which is attributed $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ transition of fluorenone unit of **HPF**. Upon concomitant addition of Cu^{2+} to receptor **HPF**, a new red shifted absorption band centered at 428 nm appears with increasing intensity which is due to com-

Fig. 3. Color changes of **HPF** (20 μM) after addition of 1.2 equiv. of various cations in 10 mM HEPES buffer- CH_3OH (99 : 1, v/v) at room temperature.

Fig. 4. Changes in the UV-Vis spectra of **HPF** (20 μM) after addition of 1.2 equiv. of various cations in 10 mM HEPES buffer- CH_3OH (99 : 1, v/v) at room temperature.

Fig. 5. Optical density of **HPF** (20 μM) at 428 nm upon the addition of different cations in 10 mM HEPES buffer- CH_3OH (99 : 1, v/v) at room temperature.

plexation of pyrimidine of **HPF** with Cu^{II} (Fig. 6). Meanwhile, the original absorption band centered at 360 nm decreases gradually, generating an isosbestic points at 389 nm, which indicates the formation of a new complex between **HPF** and Cu^{2+} . As shown in the inset of Fig. 6, a nearly linear dependence of the absorbance at 428 nm band as a function of Cu^{2+} concentration from 0 to 1.2 equiv. was observed.

Fig. 6. Absorption spectral change of **HPF** (20 μM) after addition of increasing amounts of Cu^{2+} ions (0.1, 0.2, 0.3, 0.4, 0.5, 0.6, 0.7, 0.8, 0.9, 1.0, 1.1 and 1.2 equiv.) in 10 mM HEPES buffer- CH_3OH (99 : 1, v/v) at room temperature. Inset : Absorption at 428 nm versus the number of equivalents of Cu^{2+} added.

Again, the absorption behaviour of **REF** (20 μM) exhibits initially two absorption bands at 388 and 244 nm. The compound **REF** neither observed any UV-Vis absorption spectral change nor naked-eye detection of color upon addition of Cu^{2+} (Fig. 7). From above two experiments we have concluded the indis-

Fig. 7. Changes in the UV-Vis spectra of **REF** (20 μM) after addition of increasing amounts of Cu^{2+} ions in 10 mM HEPES buffer- CH_3OH (99 : 1, v/v) at room temperature. Inset : Color change of **REF** (20 μM) after addition Cu^{2+} .

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pensable roles of the pyrimidine 'N' within receptor **HPF** and Cu^{2+} for complexation and naked-eye colour change.

We have studied the better selectivity of **HPF** as a colorimetric receptor for the recognition of Cu^{2+} in the presence of various competing metal ions. For competition studies, receptor **HPF** (20 μM) was treated with 1.2 equiv. of Cu^{2+} in the presence of 1.2 equiv. of other metal ions, as indicated in Fig. 8. There was no interference in the detection of Cu^{2+} from various competitive cations. Thus, **HPF** could be used as a selective colorimetric sensor for Cu^{2+} in the presence of most of the competing metal ions.

Fig. 8. The absorbance of **HPF** (20 μM) at 428 nm in the presence of different metal ions (1.2 equiv., dark yellow bars), and in the above solution upon addition of Cu^{2+} (1.2 equiv., navy bars) in 10 mM HEPES buffer- CH_3OH (99 : 1, v/v) at room temperature.

For further determination the stoichiometry between **HPF** and Cu^{2+} , Job's plot²⁵ analyses were also used. When molar fraction of Cu^{2+} was 0.5, the absorbance at 428 nm reaches to maximum (Fig. 9), demonstrating the formation of 1 : 1 complex between **HPF** and Cu^{2+} . For further information on the coordination mode of the **HPF**- Cu^{2+} complex, we performed ^1H NMR titration of **HPF** with Cu^{2+} , but it was not doing well owing to the paramagnetic nature of Cu^{2+} ions. Based

Fig. 9. Job's plot for the binding of receptor **HPF** and Cu^{2+} , where the intensity at 428 nm was plotted against the mole fraction of Cu^{2+} .

on the Job's plot study, we propose the structure of the **HPF**- Cu^{2+} complex as shown in Scheme 2.

Based on UV-Vis titration, the association constant²² (K) of **HPF** with Cu^{2+} ion was calculated using the Benesi-Hildebrand equation (Fig. S7 in Supplementary material). The K value turned out to be $4.69 \times 10^3 \text{ M}^{-1}$. The detection limit²³ of receptor **HPF** for the analysis of Cu^{2+} ions was calculated to be $5.03 \times 10^{-8} \text{ M}$ (Fig. S8 in Supplementary material). The de-

Scheme 2. A possible sensing mechanism of the receptor **HPF** to Cu^{2+} .

tection limit of **HPF** for Cu^{2+} was much lower than that recommended by the US EPA in drinking water (1–4 ppm). Therefore, **HPF** could be a good indicator for the detection of copper ions in the drinking water.

We investigated the effect of pH on the absorption response of receptor **HPF** to the Cu^{2+} ion in same media with pH values ranging from 2 to 12 (Fig. 10). The color of the Cu^{2+} -**HPF** complex remained in the

wine red region between pH 4 and 11, while its color changed to the original yellow at pH 2, 3 and 12. These results indicate that Cu^{2+} could be clearly detected by the naked-eye or UV-Vis absorption measurements using **HPF** over the wide pH range of 4.0–11.0. The color change of the Cu^{2+} -**HPF** complex from wine red to yellow at very low pH (2 and 3) and high pH (>11) might be due to demetallation of the complex, thus regenerating the receptor **HPF** with its yellow color.

To ensure the practical application of receptor **HPF**, test strips were ready by immersing filter papers into a methanol solution of **HPF** (20 μM) and then drying in air. These test strips were applied for sensing different Cu^{2+} concentrations (0, 10 μM , 30 μM), exhibiting

Fig. 10. Variation of absorbance intensity (428 nm) of free **HPF** (20 μM) and in the presence of Cu^{2+} ion in 10 mM HEPES buffer- CH_3OH (99 : 1, v/v) at room temperature, solution with different pH conditions.

colorimetric changes differentiable by bare eyes (Fig. 11). Development of such test strips is helpful as instantaneous qualitative information without resorting to the instrumental analysis.

To better understand the nature of the coordination of Cu^{2+} with **HPF**, energy-optimized structures of **HPF** and **HPF-Cu²⁺** (Fig. 12a) were obtained on Density Functional Theory (DFT) calculations at the B3LYP level using 6-311G** basis set for simple receptor (**HPF**) and LANL2DZ basis set for metal complex using the Gaussian 09 program²⁶. The spatial

Fig. 11. Photographs of the test kits with **HPF** for detecting Cu^{2+} ion in methanol solution with different concentrations. Left to right : 0, 10 μM , 30 μM .

distributions and orbital energies of the highest occupied molecular orbital (HOMO) and the lowest unoccupied molecular orbital (LUMO) of **HPF** and the corresponding Cu^{2+} complex were also generated using this calculations (Fig. 12b). The HOMO is spread over the whole molecule, whereas LUMO is distributed on the $-\text{C}=\text{N}$ bond and pyrimidine N in **HPF**, and the imine N and pyrimidine N are favorably coordinated with Cu^{2+} . In **HPF-Cu²⁺** complex, the π electrons of HOMO are mainly located on the $\text{C}=\text{N}$ and the LUMO is mostly spread over the pyrimidine ring. The energy gaps between the HOMO and LUMO of the probe and corresponding Cu^{2+} complex were found to be 2.094 eV and 0.184 eV, respectively (Table S3 in Supplementary material). This calculated results exhibit the red shifting absorption band compared to the free ligand which corroborates with the observed absorption spectral band position. Calculation also predicts better stabilized of **HPF-Cu²⁺** complex than the bare **HPF** ligand.

4. Conclusions

In summary, we have developed a pyrimidine based sensor **HPF**, which could detect Cu^{2+} in aqueous solution with specific selectivity and high sensitivity in a very short time. Our method is simple, rapid, cost-effective and could find potential application as a 'na-

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Fig. 12(a). Stereoscopic view of the energy optimized structures of **HPF** (left) and **HPF-Cu²⁺** (right).

Fig. 12(b). HOMO-LUMO energy gaps for respective compounds and interfacial plots of the orbitals of **HPF** (left) and **HPF-Cu²⁺** (right).

ked-eye' indicator for Cu²⁺ ions in aqueous solution. In particular, there was no interference response for detection of Cu²⁺ in the presence of competing metal ions. The detection limit of Cu²⁺ was found to be $5.03 \times 10^{-8} M$. On the other hand, the decrease in calculated HOMO-LUMO band gap energy evidences red shifted absorption band of the complex than the bare molecule which corroborates well with experimental findings and calculation also predicts stabilization of complex of receptor **HPF** with Cu²⁺. Moreover, test strips based on sensor **HPF** were fabricated, which could serve as a practical colorimetric sensor for "in-field" measurement of Cu²⁺ and does not require any labor-intensive synthetic protocols. We anticipate that

this report of a colorimetric pyrimidine-based sensor for Cu²⁺ ion could prompt the development of more sensitive and cost-effective methods for Cu²⁺ ion detection from the scientific community.

Supporting Information

Supporting Information is available in the Website : indianchemicalsociety.com.

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